

Audio Analysis Applications in the Browser with Essentia.js

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ABSTRACT

This demo will present a collection of examples and industrial applications of *Essentia.js* for audio and music analysis in the browser. It will cover their technical implementation and challenges. These web demos cover spectral and pitch descriptor visualization, onset detection, audio metering, mood classification, music genre auto-tagging, and audio quality problem detection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Essentia.js was conceived to fill a gap in web technologies for audio signal processing and MIR, with its first version released in 2020 [5]. It enabled replicating results obtained with the upstream Essentia [2] while maintaining the source algorithms in a single code base library. Since then, the library has grown in users and features, including the addition of machine learning models for music classification [3] [6].

In 2021 [4], we presented a workshop that focused on showing the basics of using *Essentia.js*. This demo aims to show a few use cases of *Essentia.js* both as product examples and industrial applications. Some of these cases were briefly shown in the 2021 workshop. Here we will go into greater detail in their technical implementation. These examples can be found on our website.¹

2. ESSENTIA.JS APPLICATIONS

2.1 Spectral and pitch analysis

This collection of demos centers on visualising basic spectral and pitch descriptors in real-time with a microphone input. It was the first set of library usage examples developed and, as such, they are the simplest in design and code

¹<https://mtg.github.io/essentia.js/examples/>

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Figure 1: Real-time pitch visualization.

architecture. Figure 1 shows a melspectrogram and pitch visualization.

2.2 Onset detection

This example application detects audio onsets on users' own audio samples or ones loaded from Freesound [7], and visualises them on top of a waveform representation (as seen on Figure 2). It allows adjusting the onsets via a few parameters that control the spectral analysis and onset detection functions used, as well as downloading the resulting audio slices as audio files. In the case of Freesound tracks, users can also share their resulting analysis with friends. Some of the development challenges involved writing specific extractors in C++ due to current limitations in the cross-compilation of the library. This extra functionality will be included in future versions of *Essentia.js*.

2.3 Audio metering

We recently developed an application that provides typical mastering metering (EBU R128 loudness standard, stereo phase and spectral profile) of finished music tracks. Users can upload a batch of up to 8 tracks for analysis, all kept locally in the browser at all times. As shown in Figure 3 the results are then visualized as cards with numeric data for

Figure 2: Onset detection from audio file or Freesound.

loudness and graphical data for stereo phase and spectral profile, and the user can select one of the tracks to use as reference so they can compare with the rest of the tracks.

2.4 Mood classification

We developed a song mood detection demo for the online music database service Tunebat.com.² Upon uploading an audio track, it uses five machine learning transfer learning models to assess the track’s danceability, happiness, sadness, relaxedness, and aggressiveness. Additionally we included BPM and key estimation algorithms in the demo, shown in Figure 4.

2.5 Real-time music autotagging

We have published a real-time music autotagging demo that uses the pretrained MusiCNN deep learning model [10] (787K trainable parameters) on a live microphone input. It produces activations for a set of 50 labels (genre and sub-genre), shown in the UI as small cards with varying opacity (see Figure 5).

We are currently finishing development of another real-time music autotagging demo. This one, however, uses a ResNet18 architecture [8] (11M trainable parameters) trained on an in-house dataset annotated with Discogs³ metadata for their 400 most popular music styles, with labels formatted as *genre—subgenre* (this is a more lightweight version of the model available in the Essentia website⁴). As shown in Figure 6, the demo visualizes the top 5 activations out the 400 possible labels, where each row of labels corresponds to a temporal frame of analysis.

2.6 Audio quality problems

This application (Figure 7) demonstrates a use case for SonoSuite S.L.,⁵ where their users upload a track to the website to be analysed in the client and detect any abnormality in the audio file [9]. The audio problems algorithms in *Essentia* [1] help the artist and the quality control agents from SonoSuite to make decisions prior to the distribution of the music.

3. DEMO REQUIREMENTS

All these demos run on most modern browser. We recommend using Chrome and Firefox for best performance.

²<https://tunebat.com/>

³<https://www.discogs.com/>

⁴<https://essentia.upf.edu/models.html#discogs-effnet>

⁵<https://sonosuite.com>

Figure 3: Audio metering demo results cards.

Figure 4: Mood classification demo.

Figure 5: Autotagging with MusicCNN.

Figure 6: Autotagging with Discogs ResNet.

Figure 7: Audio quality problems demo.

The technical requirements for the demo are:

- Space for one laptop (brought by author), with mains power.
- Stereo sound system, either monitors or headphones
- Projector / screen (HDMI)

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